

Molar Volumes of Ammonium Acetate-Ammonium Salt (NH_4Cl , NH_4Br , NH_4NO_3) Solutions

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The apparent molar volume, φ_v , of ammonium chloride, ammonium bromide and ammonium nitrate has been determined in various solutions of ammonium acetate at 35° from density measurements using an hydrostatic balance. The φ_v values of NH_4X ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , NO_3^-) in $\text{NH}_4\text{OOCCH}_3$ solutions is a linear functions of concentration. The mean apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , of $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions have also been estimated directly from density measurements as well as from pure water data using Young's rule. The deviations are approximately studied as excess volume of mixing, ΔV_m , of NH_4X with $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$.

DURING recent years, volume studies in mixed electrolyte solutions have been extensively reported for understanding the interactions prevailing among electrolytes¹⁻⁶. However, little attention has been paid to the investigation of the behaviour of non-electrolyte-electrolyte solutions. The mean apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , of non-electrolyte-electrolyte solutions have been correctly estimated as a first approximation from molar volume data of these salts in pure water using additivity rule developed by Young⁷. The Young's rule when applied to non-electrolyte-electrolyte mixture is given by⁸

$$\phi_v = \sum_i Y_i \varphi_v(i) \quad \dots (1)$$

where ϕ_v is the mean apparent molal volume of the solution, $\varphi_v(i)$ is the apparent molal volume for the component (i) in water at the same ionic strength as the total mixture and Y_i is the molal weighting factor ($Y_i = m_i/m_T$) where m_i is the molality of the component i and $m_T = \sum m_i$ is the total molality. The formula has been shown to hold for various multicomponent solutions. The object of the present investigation has been to verify Young's rule for mixtures of ammonium salts and to study deviations, if any from Young's rule in terms of excess volume of mixing of non-electrolyte-electrolyte solutions at constant ionic strength.

Experimental

Ammonium chloride, ammonium bromide, ammonium nitrate and ammonium acetate used in the present investigation were of AnalaR grade and were used without further purification. Water of specific conductance $10^{-6} \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ was used for making different solutions. The densities of the solutions were measured with a hydrostatic balance similar to that of Millero⁹. The details of calculations for measuring densities with this method are given elsewhere⁴. The accuracy was checked by measuring density of pure dioxane at 30°. Our

value, $d = 1.02230(4) \text{ gm.cm}^{-3}$ is in good agreement with literature⁹ value of $d = 1.02230 \text{ gm.cm}^{-3}$. A difference in weight of float in water and dioxane at 30° was $\pm 3.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ gm}$. All measurements reported in the present study were carried out at 35° using water bath placed in an air thermostat.

Results and Discussion

The densities have been measured for $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{NH}_4\text{Br}$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4-\text{NH}_4\text{X}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , NO_3^-) solutions at 35° at different concentrations. The apparent molal volume, φ_v , of NH_4Cl , NH_4Br , NH_4NO_3 in $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions were calculated directly from density data with the equation

$$\varphi_v = \frac{1000(d^\circ - d)}{m d d^\circ} + \frac{M}{d} \quad \dots (2)$$

where m is the molality of NH_4X in $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions, d is the density of the solution, d° is the density of the solvent ($\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions at $m=0$) and M is the molecular weight of NH_4X . The apparent molal volumes of NH_4X ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , NO_3^-), calculated in this manner have been found to vary linearly with m in different $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions at 35°.

The plots of φ_v vs m for $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are shown in Fig. 1. The apparent molal volume at infinite dilution has been calculated for different solutions from extrapolation of the linear plots of φ_v vs m . These values are given in Table 1.

The volume properties of multicomponent solutions can also be conveniently treated⁸ by using the concept of mean apparent molar volume, ϕ_v . The mean apparent molal volume, ϕ_v is given by⁸

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d^\circ - d)}{m_T d d^\circ} + \frac{M_T}{d} \quad \dots (3)$$

TABLE 1—THE PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUME AT INFINITE DILUTION FOR NH_4Cl , NH_4Br , NH_4NO_3 IN $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ SOLUTIONS AT 35°

$m\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$	$\varphi_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$	$S_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{Cl})$	$\varphi_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{Br})$	$S_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{Br})$	$\varphi_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3)$	$S_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3)$
0	38.40	13.12	45.20	22.64	50.40	14.84
0.01	—	—	44.20	-20.87	42.80	22.85
0.08	38.90	-13.30	47.00	-26.66	39.00	40.00
0.05	37.50	- 8.10	49.60	-32.43	36.60	48.50
0.07	35.80	8.15	52.80	-40.00	—	—
0.09	33.70	11.17	56.80	-48.00	—	—

$\varphi_v^\circ(\text{NH}_4\text{Ac}) = 46.20$; $S_v^\circ(\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4) = 20.20$ (where S_v° stands for the limiting slope of the plots of ϕ_v vs m).

 Fig. 1. Plot of ϕ_v vs m for $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions at 35° .

where d° is the density of pure water, d is the density of the solution, m_T is the total molality and M_T is the mean molecular weight. M_T of a solution is determined by equation (4) :

$$M_T = \sum \frac{Y_i M_i}{1} \quad \dots (4)$$

where M_i is the molecular weight of the component i and Y_i is the molal weighting factor. The mean apparent molal volumes ϕ_v of $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ were determined by using equation (3) and are given as a function of salt concentration as plotted in Fig. 2.

The curves representing various concentrations of NH_4X solutions in $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions could not be extrapolated to a point corresponding to zero concentration of NH_4X salts. This only suggests that there is a lot of solute-solute interactions in these multicomponent-electrolyte mixtures and ϕ_v° cannot be considered to be made-up of two components.

Millero² used Young's method⁷ to estimate mean apparent molar properties of mixed electrolyte solutions through the consideration of the weighted additivity of the properties of electrolyte

 Fig. 2. Plot of ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{m_T}$ for $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions at 35° .

components in pure water to be equal to the properties of mixed electrolyte solutions. If we apply this to our present system, the mean apparent molal volume can be calculated from equation (5) :

$$\phi_v(\text{cal}) = Y_{\text{NH}_4\text{X}} \varphi_v(\text{NH}_4\text{X}) + Y_{\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4} \varphi_v(\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4) \quad \dots (5)$$

where $\phi_v(\text{cal})$ is the mean apparent molal volume calculated from pure water apparent molal volume data, $Y_{\text{NH}_4\text{X}} = m_{\text{NH}_4\text{X}}/m_T$, $Y_{\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4} = m_{\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4}/m_T$, $\varphi_v(\text{NH}_4\text{X})$ is the apparent molal volume of NH_4X in water at m_T . $\varphi_v(\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4)$ is the apparent molal volume of $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ in water at m_T . The $\phi_v(\text{cal})$ of $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions determined from (5) are also contained in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3. Plot of ΔV_m vs Y_B for $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions at 35° .

The observed value for ϕ_v and $\phi_v(\text{cal})$ can be related by the relation :

$$\phi_v(\text{obs}) - \phi_v(\text{cal}) = \Delta\phi_v(\text{excess}) \quad \dots (6)$$

$\Delta\phi_v(\text{excess})$ has large magnitude and it appears that there is considerable change in the volumes of non-electrolyte-electrolyte solutions on mixing. The

volume of mixing, ΔV_m , calculated from equation (7) :

$$\Delta\phi_v(\text{excess}) = \frac{\Delta V_m}{m_T} \quad \dots (7)$$

for $\text{NH}_4\text{X}-\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions are plotted vs Y_B ($Y_B = m_B/m_T$) in Fig. 3.

This has been found to be of large magnitude but parabolic curve with maxima around $Y_B = 0.5$, for different $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ solutions is similar to the curves for volume of mixing of other compounds. The large value of ΔV_m may be attributed to the non-validity of equation (5).

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